

Funded by
the European Union

Organisation [DLR]

Department [Institute of Solar Research]

Deliverable 3.1

Fast-Track School Materials

SALTOpower

Date: 18.02.2025

Doc. Version: 3

Document Control Information

Settings	Value
Document Title:	Fast-Track School Materials
Project Title:	SALTOpower
Document Author:	Eckhard Lüpfer (DLR)
Project Owner:	European Commission
Project Manager:	Pedro Horta (UEVORA)
Doc. Version:	1
Sensitivity:	Public
Date:	18.02.2025

Document Approver(s) and Reviewer(s):

NOTE: All Approvers are required. Records of each approver must be maintained. All Reviewers in the list are considered required unless explicitly listed as Optional.

Name	Role	Action	Date
Pedro Horta (UEVORA)	PM	<i>Approved conditionally</i>	19.02.2025
Marco D'Auria (ENEA)	PSC	<i>Approved conditionally</i>	19.02.2025
Eckhard Lüpfer (DLR)	PSC	<i>Approved conditionally</i>	19.02.2025

Document history:

The Document Author is authorised to make the following types of changes to the document without requiring that the document be re-approved:

- Editorial, formatting, and spelling
- Clarification

To request a change to this document, contact the Document Author or Owner.

Changes to this document are summarised in the following table in reverse chronological order (latest version first).

Revision	Date	Created by	Short Description of Changes

Configuration Management: Document Location

The latest version of this controlled document is stored in *project folder*.

TABLE OF CONTENTS

1. Introduction	3
2. Fast-Track Schools Overview	3
2.1. FTS #1 Molten salt basic research topics and State-of-the-Art	4
2.1.1 Photos	6
2.2. FTS #2 Molten salt experimental procedures and implementation	6
2.2.1 Photos	9
2.3. FTS #3 Technology benchmarking and Exploitation	9
2.3.1. Photos	12
3. Evaluation	12
Annex 1: Related Documents	14
Annex 2: Satisfaction surveys	15

1. INTRODUCTION

In fulfilment of the SALTOpower¹ Grant Agreement on the obligations of the Consortium towards the Project Owner (PO) regarding project deliverables, the current document stands as Deliverable 3.1 Fast Track School Materials, as described in the project Description of Action (Part A).

Task 3.1 aims at the development of molten salt training materials and the implementation of three Fast-Track School (FTS) editions.

2. FAST-TRACK SCHOOLS OVERVIEW

The objectives and philosophy of the Fast-track Schools were evolutive training along with the project for candidates and young researchers. Training materials have been developed with the focus of the three editions under the title “Molten salt technologies and energy system applications”:

1. Molten salt basic research topics and State-of-the-Art
(May 2023, ENEA Casaccia Research Centre Rome);
2. Molten salt experimental procedures and implementation
(July 2024, DLR Research Centre Cologne);
3. Technology benchmarking and Exploitation
(November 2024, University of Évora).

The Fast-Track School (FTS) lecture contents and brainstorming moderation were assured by teams involving all the Consortium partners.

The coordination of FTS teams included

- Senior Researchers for the Young Researcher School focused on SALTOpower JRA;
- Young Researchers for the Candidate Researcher School focused on SALTOpower PhD Thesis.

FTS materials constitute this Deliverable D3.1 – “Complete and revised public version set of training materials used in the three editions of the Fast Track Schools” and are publically available on SALTOpower Zenodo (<https://zenodo.org/communities/saltopower/>) and website (<https://www.saltopower.uevora.pt/media/#presentations>). These training materials, as well as

¹ Project: 101079303 — SALTOpower — HORIZON-WIDERA-2021-ACCESS-03

photos, attendance lists, satisfaction survey results, FTS agendas and Zoom records, are stored in the internal shared folder (SharePoint), according to the SALTOpower Data Management Plan.

2.1. FTS #1 Molten salt basic research topics and State-of-the-Art

This first edition of the SALTOpower Fast-Track School was held at ENEA’s Casaccia Research Centre in Rome, Italy, in May 2023 and the agenda was as presented in Figure 1.

SALTOpower FTS #1: Program Molten Salt (MS) basic research topics and State of the Art

Day 1		09.05.2023
Audience: Industry, Candidate Young Researchers, Young Researchers		
14.00	Welcome & Introduction	Walter Gaggioli & Michela Lanchi (ENEA)
14.10	Overview of MS use in CSP plants	Jana Stangler (DLR)
14.30	MS potential in Process heat applications	Pedro Horta (UEvora)
14.50	Coffee break	
15.15	Salt mixtures for MS applications (20 min + Q&A)	Anna Chiara Tizzoni (ENEA)
15.45	Solar Salt – Pushing an old material for energy storage to a new limit (20 min + Q&A)	Alexander Bonk (DLR)
16.15	Compatibility of MS with metallic materials: Corrosion procedures (20 min + Q&A)	Elisabetta Veca (ENEA)
16.45	End	

Day 2		10.05.2023
Audience: Candidate Young Researchers, Young Researchers		
09.00	Molten Salts as HTF for chemical reactors (20 min + Q&A)	Luca Turchetti (ENEA)
09.30	MS potential in Carnot Battery concepts (20 min + Q&A)	Radia El Cadi (UEvora)
10.00	MS suitable components: requirements and operation (20 min + Q&A)	Marco D'Auria (ENEA)
10.30	Coffee break	
11.00	MS thermal energy storage: from current two-tank systems to thermocline technology (20 min + Q&A)	Christian Odenthal (DLR)
11.30	Potential new applications for MS storage beyond CSP (20 min + Q&A)	Thomas Bauer (DLR)
12.00	Lessons learned from the commissioning/management of CSP MS plants operation	Valeria Russo (ENEA)
12.30	Lunch break	
14.00	Technical visit to ENEA Research Infrastructure	On-site attendants only
15.30	Researchers' brainstorming	
17.00	End	

Figure 1. FTS#1 agenda.

The presentations were the following:

- **Overview of MS use in CSP plants** by Jana Stangler (DLR).
- **MS potential in Process heat applications** by Pedro Horta (UÉvora).
- **Salt mixtures for MS applications** by Anna Chiara Tizzoni (ENEA).
- **Solar Salt – Pushing an old material for energy storage to a new limit** by Alexander Bonk (DLR).
- **Compatibility of MS with metallic materials: Corrosion procedures** by Elisabetta Veca (ENEA).
- **Molten Salts as HTF for chemical reactors** by Luca Turchetti (ENEA).
- **MS potential in Carnot Battery concepts** by Radia El Cadi (UÉvora).
- **MS suitable components: requirements and operation** by Marco D'Auria (ENEA).
- **MS thermal energy storage: from current two-tank systems to thermocline technology** by Christian Odenthal (DLR).
- **Potential new applications for MS storage beyond CSP** by Thomas Bauer (DLR).
- **Lessons learned from the commissioning/management of CSP MS plants operation** by Valeria Russo (ENEA).

During the second day of the FTS#1, a visit to ENEA Research Infrastructure was made and a brainstorming with the participation of the CYRs and the YRs.

All the presentations and their recordings are publicly available (see ANNEX 1).

2.1.1 Photos

More info is available on the website (<https://www.saltpower.uevora.pt/fast-track-school-1-in-rome/>).

2.2. FTS #2 Molten salt experimental procedures and implementation

The second edition of the SALTOpower Fast-Track School was held at DLR's Research Centre in Cologne, Germany, in July 2024 and the agenda was as presented in Figure 2.

The event included visits to the Institutes of Solar Research, and of Engineering Thermodynamics with the installations.

SALTOpower FTS #2: Program
Molten Salt (MS) experimental procedures and implementation

Day 1		03.07.2024
Audience: Industry, Candidate Young Researchers, Young Researchers		
09.00	Welcome & Introduction	(DLR)
I. Prototype Testing		
09.15	TESIS facility	Christian Odenthal (DLR)
09.45	MOSE Facility: general experience in molten salt management	Giuseppe Petroni (ENEA)
10.15	MS Loop operation at 620°C	Freerk Klasing (DLR)
10.45	Coffee break	
II. Lab-scale experiments ("mg to kg scale")		
11.15	What can we learn from laboratory tests	Thomas Bauer (DLR)
11.45	Methods of characterization and prediction for molten salt mixtures: thermochemical properties, thermal stability and corrosion issues	Anna Chiara Tizzoni (ENEA)
12.30	Lunch break	
III. Melting and Freezing Procedures		
14.00	Melting and freezing procedures TESIS test facility	Christian Odenthal (DLR)
14.30	Salt melting procedures in PCS facility	Valeria Russo (ENEA)
15.00	HPS2 salt handling procedures: melting and freezing operations, NOx emissions, foaming, salt handling, shift operation	Radia Ait El Cadi (UEvora)
15.30	Coffee break	
16.00	Overview and comparison on different approaches in ENEA/DLR/UEvora facilities	Pedro Horta (UEvora)
16.30	End	

Day 2		04.07.2024
Audience: Candidate Young Researchers, Young Researchers		
IV. Large-scale experiments (“full-size loops with solar concentration”)		
09.00	MATS facility	Raffaele Liberatore (ENEA)
09.30	EMSP Facility: Control and monitoring	Radia Ait El Cadi (UEvora)
10.00	Coffee break	
10.30	HPS2 hibernation concepts	Niklas Dicke (DLR)
11.00	Preventive and corrective maintenance	Paula Martins (UEvora)
11.30	Researchers' Brainstorm	
12.30	Lunch break	
14.00	Technical visit to DLR Research Infrastructure	On-site attendants only, Christian Odenthal, Thomas Bauer (DLR)
16.30	End	

Figure 2. FTS#2 agenda.

The presentations were the following:

- **TESIS facility** by Christian Odenthal (DLR).
- **MOSE Facility: general experience in molten salt management** by Giuseppe Petroni (ENEA).
- **MS Loop operation at 620°C** by Freerk Klasing (DLR).
- **What can we learn from laboratory tests** by Thomas Bauer (DLR).
- **Methods of characterization and prediction for molten salt mixtures: thermochemical properties, thermal stability and corrosion issues** by Anna Chiara Tizzoni (ENEA).
- **Melting and freezing procedures TESIS test facility** by Christian Odenthal (DLR).
- **Salt melting procedures in PCS facility** by Valeria Russo (ENEA).
- **HPS2 salt handling procedures: melting and freezing operations, NOx emissions, foaming, salt handling, shift operation** by Radia Ait El Cadi (UÉvora).
- **Overview and comparison on different approaches in ENEA/DLR/UÉvora facilities** by Pedro Horta (UÉvora).
- **MATS facility** by Raffaele Liberatore (ENEA).
- **EMSP Facility: Control and monitoring** by Radia Ait El Cadi (UÉvora).
- **HPS2 hibernation concepts** by Niklas Dicke (DLR).
- **Preventive and corrective maintenance** by Paula Martins (UÉvora).

During the second day of the FTS#2, a brainstorming session took place, debating the topics worked on.

All the presentations and their recordings are publicly available (see ANNEX 1).

2.2.1 Photos

More info is available on the website (<https://www.saltopower.uevora.pt/fast-track-school-2-in-cologne/>).

2.3. FTS #3 Technology benchmarking and Exploitation

The third and final SALTOpower Fast-Track School was held at the University of Évora, Portugal, in November 2024 and the agenda was as presented in Figure 3.

SALTOpower FTS #3: Program
Molten Salt use cases, risks, bankability and new approaches

Day 1		13.11.2024
09.15	Welcome & Introduction	Pedro Horta Dominique Livreiro (UEVORA)
I. Routes to market		
09.30	Innovation and entrepreneurship for young researchers Innovation and entrepreneurship for young researchers	Hernâni Oliveira (UEvora)
II. Bankability		
10.00	Project Finance of MS storage projects	Martin Scheuerer (Protarget AG)
10.30	CSP Project Types and Bankability Considerations	Johannes Kretschmann (Fichtner)
11.00	Coffee break	
III. Molten Salt Use cases: State of the Art		
11.30	Overview of Molten Salt applications in Concentrating Solar Power plants	Radia Ait El Cadi (UEVORA)
12.00	Molten Salt applications in other sectors	Francesco Rovense (ENEA)
12.30	Lunch break	
IV. Technology Risks		
14.00	Salt handling, leakage, NOx emissions	Paula Martins (UEVORA)
14.30	Mechanical and corrosion risks	Anna Chiara Tizzoni /

		Elisabetta Veca (ENEA)
V. New technological approaches		
15.00	600°C Nitrate salts operations at HPMS2 Molten Salt Tower Receiver Testing Jülich	Kathrin Ingenwepelt (DLR)
15.30	Coffee break	
15.50	Development and potential market launch of new molten salt technologies	Wenjin Ding (DLR)
16.20	Electrical heaters for high renewables coverage	Nitha Sriitharen (DLR)
17.00	End	

Day 2 - FTS#3		14.11.2024
09.30	Researchers' Brainstorm	On-site attendants only
11.00	Coffee break	
11.20	Researchers' Brainstorm	On-site attendants only
12.50	Lunch break	
14.15	Technical visit to UEVORA Research Infrastructure	On-site attendants only - bus
17.30	End	

Figure 3. FTS#3 agenda.

The presentations were the following:

- **Innovation and entrepreneurship for young researchers** Innovation and entrepreneurship for young researchers by Hernâni Oliveira (UÉvora).
- **Project Finance of MS storage projects** by Martin Scheuerer (Protarget AG).
- **CSP Project Types and Bankability Considerations** by Johannes Kretschmann (Fichtner).
- **Overview of Molten Salt applications in Concentrating Solar Power plants** by Radia Ait El Cadi (UÉvora).
- **Molten Salt applications in other sectors** by Francesco Rovense (ENEA).
- **Salt handling, leakage, NOx emissions** by Paula Martins (UÉvora).
- **Mechanical and corrosion risks** by Anna Chiara Tizzoni and Elisabetta Veca (ENEA).
- **600°C Nitrate salts operations at HPMS2 Molten Salt Tower Receiver Testing Jülich** by Kathrin Ingenwepelt (DLR).
- **Development and potential market launch of new molten salt technologies** by Wenjin Ding (DLR).
- **Electrical heaters for high renewables coverage** by Nithaarshini Sriitharen (DLR).

As in the previous editions, it is worth noting that both in the presentations on the first day and in the brainstorming session on the second day, the participation of the CYRs and the YRs was very active. They were not mere listeners but gave talks, and were the protagonists of the brainstorming.

All the presentations and their recordings will be publicly available (see ANNEX 1).

2.3.1. Photos

More info is available on the website (<https://www.saltopower.uevora.pt/fast-track-school-3-in-evora/>).

3. EVALUATION

The three events at the three different locations of the project partners have always been relevant meetings for the project partners and their scientific staff and have improved the collaboration between the involved teams and institutes. More importantly, external participants from other research institutions and the industry have joined the meetings, and listened to the presentations – a significant number on site – and this way contributed to the strengthening of the network and collaboration towards future exploitation of the project achievements.

The table below depicts the registrations and attendees to the three Fast-Track School editions.

Table 1. Summary of registrations and attendance to the three FTS editions.

Fast-Track School edition	Registrations	Attendance			
		onsite	online	Total	Success criteria
FTS#1	99	21	38	59	15 (good)
FTS#2	76	26	25	51*	20 (very good)
FTS#3	60	22	22	44**	25 (excellent)

*Number of repetitions 8.

**Number of repetitions 24.

Considering the project success criteria for this task (right column), we can consider that the FTS editions have exceeded all expectations.

A satisfaction survey with 16 questions (plus 6 questions only for the onsite attendants, regarding the brainstorming sessions) was delivered to the attendees at the end of the FTS, and the results are summarized in Tables 2 and 3.

Table 2. Summary of FTS satisfaction survey results (onsite and online attendants).

Fast-Track School edition	Number of answers	Satisfaction rate (out of 5)
FTS#1	15	4,20
FTS#2	27	4,45
FTS#3	9	4,44

Table 3. Summary of Brainstorming satisfaction survey results (only onsite attendants).

Fast-Track School edition	Number of answers	Satisfaction rate (out of 5)
FTS#1	6	4
FTS#2	18	3,67
FTS#3	7	4,15

These results also confirm the success of this activity of the SALTOpower project (see ANNEX 2).

ANNEX 1: RELATED DOCUMENTS

All the FTS materials are available for the project partners in a shared drive located in SharePoint.

The videos and presentations of the three FTS are publicly available on the **SALTOpower project website** and **Zenodo**.

ID	Reference or <Related Document>	Source or <Link/Location>
1	Project folder	
2	Project Description of Action (Part A) <101079303_Annex 1 - Description of the action (part A).pdf>	Project folder
3	Project Description of Action (Part B) <101079303_Annex 1 - Description of the action (part B).pdf>	Project folder
4	Data Management Plan <SALTOPOWER_D_1_2_DATA_MANAGEMENT_PLAN_05-05-2023_v_2>	Project folder
5	SALTOpower project website FTS videos	https://www.saltopower.uevora.pt/media/#videos
6	SALTOpower project website FTS presentations	https://www.saltopower.uevora.pt/media/#presentations
7	SALTOpower Zenodo	https://zenodo.org/communities/saltopower

ANNEX 2: SATISFACTION SURVEYS

FTS#1

SALTOpower Fast-Track School

15 Responses 03:20 Average time to complete Active Status

1. How did you hear about this event?

Promotional email	2
Social Networks	0
Word of mouth	0
Colleagues	8
Other	5

2. Overall, how satisfied are you with SALTOpower Fast-Track School Experience?

15
Responses

3. How useful was the information provided in the event program (Agenda, venue, registration)?

15
Responses

4. Were the topics of the School useful for you?

15
Responses

★★★★☆
4.27 Average Rating

5. Which presentation focus did you like most?

● Materials	8
● Components	4
● Systems	5
● Applications	9

6. Was the overall timing of the event appropriate?

15
Responses

★★★★☆
4.20 Average Rating

7. Was the timing (duration, start and end time) of the talks and Q&A session appropriate for the content?

15
Responses

★★★★☆
4.27 Average Rating

8. How would you rate the technical skills of the speakers?

15
Responses

★★★★★
4.60 Average Rating

9. How would you rate the communication skills of the speakers?

15
Responses

★ ★ ★ ★ ☆
4.13 Average Rating

10. Do you have any suggestion to improve the event or strengthen topics for the next Fast-Track School?

15
Responses

Latest Responses

"no"

"no"

:"

11. How likely would you participate in the next Fast-Track School?

15
Responses

★ ★ ★ ★ ☆
4.27 Average Rating

12. How likely would you recommend to participate in the next Fast-Track School to others?

15
Responses

★ ★ ★ ★ ☆
4.33 Average Rating

13. Age:

18-30	9
31-40	3
41-50	2
51-60	1
>60	0

14. Job title:

Engineer	4
Researcher	3
PhD student	2
MSc student	1
Professor	0
Other	5

15. Sector:

Industry	5
University	6
Public research and technolog...	4
Private research and technolo...	0
Other	0

16. I attended the event:

On-Site	5
Online	10

17. Was the visit to the research infrastructures interesting to you?

5
Responses

★★★★★
4.60 Average Rating

Researchers' Brainstorming

6 Responses 01:53 Average time to complete **Active** Status

1. How satisfied are you with Researchers' Brainstorming session?

6
Responses

2. Do you find useful creating a network to share opportunities in the research field?

6
Responses

3. Which is the best way to keep this network updated and increasing engagement of the participants?

- Email 5
- LinkedIn / Social network 5
- Online meetings 4
- Presencial meetings 2
- Workshops 3

4. How useful do you think it is to involve people outside of SALTOpower Consortium in the network?

6
Responses

★ ★ ★ ★ ☆
4.33 Average Rating

5. Do you have any suggestion to improve the next SALTOpower events?

5
Responses

Latest Responses
"Increase practical sessions"
"none"
"no"

6. Indicate the most important opportunities offered by this network:

- Getting enrolled in a PhD pro... 0
- Getting new job opportunities 1
- Visiting relevant research infra... 4
- Enhancing personal and profes... 6

FTS#2

1. How did you hear about this event?

27 respostas

- Promotional email
- Social Networks
- Word of mouth
- Colleagues
- Other

2. Overall, how satisfied are you with the SALTOpower Fast-Track School Experience? (1 - strongly unsatisfied ... 5 - strongly satisfied)

27 respostas

3. How useful was the information provided in the event program (agenda, venue, registration)? (1 - not useful ... 5 - very useful)

27 respostas

4. Were the topics of the Fast-Track School useful for you? (1 - not useful ... 5 - very useful)

27 respostas

5. Which presentation focus did you like most?

27 respostas

6. Was the overall timing of the event appropriate? (1 - not appropriate ... 5 - very appropriate)

27 respostas

7. Was the talks and Q&A session timing (duration, start, and end time) appropriate for the content? (1 - strongly disagree ... 5 - strongly agree)

27 respostas

8. How would you rate the communication skills of the speakers? (1 - poor ... 5 - very good)

27 respostas

9. Do you have any suggestions to improve the event or strengthen topics for the next Fast-Track School?

7 respostas

Introduction of each other at the beginning, bigger room, better equipment, checking earlier if everything is working correctly, maybe the speaker who leading the conference could be also one time a men and then a woman ?

Digital Twin Tech. & ai & computational chemistry

More practical case studies

Active working session should be included.
Get to know at the beginning.

Give opportunitie to the students to present their work master or Phd.

The showed practical experiences have bene very interesting

Everyone should use spell-checking before presenting.

10. How likely would you participate in the next Fast-Track Schools (considering having no financial, time, etc. constraints)? (1 - not likely ... 5 - very likely)

27 respostas

10.1. what kind of constraints might you have?

26 respostas

11. How likely would you recommend participating in the next Fast-Track Schools to others? (1 - not likely ... 5 - very likely)

27 respostas

12. Age:

27 respostas

13. Sector:
27 respostas

- University
- Public research and technology organization
- Industry
- Private research and technology organization
- Other

14. Job title:
27 respostas

- Engineer
- Researcher
- PhD student
- MSc student
- Professor
- Other

15. I attended the event:
27 respostas

- On-site
- Online

17. How satisfied are you with the Brainstorming? (1 - strongly unsatisfied ... 5 - strongly satisfied)

18 respostas

18. Do you find it useful to create a network to share opportunities in the research field? (1 - not useful ... 5 - very useful)

18 respostas

19. Which is the best way to keep this network updated and increase the engagement of the participants?

18 respostas

20. Indicate the most important opportunities offered by this network:

18 respostas

FTS#3

1. How did you hear about this event?

9 respostas

2. Overall, how satisfied are you with the SALTOpower Fast-Track School Experience? (1 - strongly unsatisfied ... 5 - strongly satisfied)

9 respostas

3. How useful was the information provided in the event program (agenda, venue, registration)? (1 - not useful ... 5 - very useful)

9 respostas

4. Were the topics of the Fast-Track School useful for you? (1 - not useful ... 5 - very useful)

9 respostas

5. Which presentation focus did you like most?

9 respostas

6. Was the overall timing of the event appropriate? (1 - not appropriate ... 5 - very appropriate)

9 respostas

7. Was the talks and Q&A session timing (duration, start, and end time) appropriate for the content? (1 - strongly disagree ... 5 - strongly agree)

9 respostas

8. How would you rate the communication skills of the speakers? (1 - poor ... 5 - very good)

9 respostas

9. Do you have any suggestions to improve the event or strengthen topics for the next Fast-Track School?

3 respostas

Include more competitiveness information and include molten salt users to share overall opinion on real case installations

Please send the agenda on time, like max. 3 weeks before starting event. It is better for Organisation - travel etc

it was hard to hear questions online. Debates re always the juice of such events.

10. Age:

9 respostas

11. Sector:

9 respostas

12. Job title:

9 respostas

13. I attended the event:

9 respostas

14. How satisfied are you with the Brainstorming? (1 - strongly unsatisfied ... 5 - strongly satisfied)

7 respostas

15. Do you find it useful to create a network to share opportunities in the research field? (1 - not useful ... 5 - very useful)

7 respostas

16. Which is the best way to keep this network updated and increase the engagement of the participants?

7 respostas

17. Indicate the most important opportunities offered by this network:

7 respostas

